

Can self-reported seasonality predict longitudinally assessed seasonal changes of mood, food cravings, body weight, insomnia, and physical activity?

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To ensure the anonymity of participants, particularly given the small population size in the Icelandic area from which they were drawn, we are unable to provide open data.

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Ethics approval statement:

All participants provided written informed consent as part of the first page of the online form, and the study followed the Declaration of Helsinki. The National Bioethics Committee of Iceland approved the study (approval number 21-088-S1; date of approval: 13.04.2021).

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Abstract

Intro: Controversy about seasonal affective disorder lies in the poor match between its definition and the available screening methods, as well as little knowledge about the predictive value of specific seasonal symptoms assessed by those methods. We examined whether the overall score as well as sub-domains of the seasonal pattern assessment questionnaire can predict seasonal changes in mood, sleep, appetite, weight, and physical activity.

Methods: In a sample of 336 Icelandic residents, we administered an online questionnaire once in each season including the seasonal pattern assessment questionnaire, the depression, anxiety and stress scale, the Questionnaire on Cravings for Sweet or Rich Foods, the Bergen Insomnia scale, the International Physical Activity Questionnaire, and surveyed body height and weight. We compared participants with at least moderate seasonal changes to a control group of participants without seasonal changes.

Results: Only food cravings and physical activity showed seasonal fluctuations. In none of the domains the seasonal fluctuations were predictable by summer-time self-reported seasonal symptoms, neither in terms of general seasonal changes nor in the specific domain.

Conclusion: While the overall low rate of seasonal changes limits conclusions, this study adds to the literature that raises doubts about the concept of predictability of seasonal changes by self-reports.

Keywords: seasonality, seasonal affective disorder, food cravings, insomnia, seasonal weight changes, physical activity

1. Introduction

Seasonal changes in daylight availability and weather significantly impact various aspects of health and well-being, with many people experiencing fluctuations in mood (Kasper et al., 1989), food cravings (Folwarczny et al., 2022), body weight (Kuzmenko et al., 2021), sleep patterns (Seidler et al., 2023), and physical activity levels (Ma et al., 2006) throughout the year. These seasonal fluctuations have considerable socioeconomic impacts, such as higher rates of sick leave and reduced workplace productivity during winter (Pjrek et al., 2016; Winkler et al., 2019). To provide appropriate care for those particularly affected by these seasonal influences, it is crucial to estimate the severity of seasonal changes and predict the acute need for care in advance. This foresight would allow for the implementation of preventive measures aiming to reduce the adverse effects on individuals and society.

Estimates on the severity of seasonal symptoms are often conducted via self-rating questionnaires such as the Seasonal Health Questionnaire (Thomson & Cowan, 2001) and the Seasonal Pattern Assessment Questionnaire (SPAQ; Icelandic version: Magnusson, 1996), which estimates seasonal variations of health-related areas such as body weight or sleep quality and provides a global seasonality score (GSS). While the instrument is said to screen for seasonal affective disorder, the scale assesses specific self-reported seasonal changes in mood, appetite, weight, sleep, energy, and social behavior at a single time point (i.e., when the questionnaire is filled out). This approach allows for an economical estimate of seasonal symptoms without the need to observe behavior longitudinally throughout all seasons. However, this method has two main limitations. Firstly, seasonal affective disorder is defined as depression occurring annually at the same time of the year (DSM-V; American Psychiatric Association, 2013), but the instrument with 6 item screens for mood *and* for symptoms that are not necessarily indicative for depression. Therefore, a high seasonality score can indicate a high level of seasonal changes in appetite and sleep, but maybe no seasonal changes of mood. Therefore, the Seasonal Health Questionnaire (Thomson & Cowan, 2001) is better suited to screen for seasonal affective disorder, as it is oriented towards the depressive aspect in line with the DSM-V definition, yielding a higher specificity. With respect to the SPAQ it is better to refer to the obtained score as a more general *seasonality score*, as implied in the name GSS. This score allows to measure seasonal changes beyond the typical symptoms of depression, but is not a specific index for seasonal depression. Secondly, such self-report assessments may be subject to recall biases and rely on the assumption that people can either accurately recall seasonal symptoms or predict how much they will be affected by seasonal changes (Øverland et al., 2020). It is, therefore, possible that seasonal symptoms are overestimated when assessed at a single time point (Thompson et al., 2004). To avoid recall biases and inaccuracies in self-reported seasonality estimates, previous research has employed repeated assessments throughout the year, either longitudinally or cross-sectionally, instead of evaluating seasonality at a single time point. This approach has been used to study seasonal fluctuations in mood (Magnusson et al., 2000), food consumption and body weight (Kräuchi and Wirz-Justice, 1988), sleep (Seidler et al., 2023), and physical activity levels (Peiró-Velert et al., 2008).

Magnusson et al. (2000) assessed mood of over 2,000 participants in Iceland cross-sectionally, with $n > 500$ per season. The authors found no increased depression in winter compared to summer. Because mood was assessed in each season, recall biases cannot explain these null effects. However, the study is limited by the cross-sectional design, due to which a different cohort of people participated in the survey in each season. The study does not determine whether people who report higher seasonal fluctuations of mood experience more pronounced mood changes from season to season. In contrast, a longitudinal study with a large sample ($n = 5282$) from the general Dutch population found small seasonal mood changes (Winthorst et al., 2020). However, it remains unknown whether people experiencing more pronounced seasonal fluctuations in mood are aware of the severity and thus

provide higher seasonality ratings compared to those whose mood exhibits less variation throughout the year.

In addition to mood, longitudinal studies have also explored the seasonal fluctuations of appetite, food cravings, and body weight (Kräuchi and Wirz-Justice, 1988; Visscher and Seidel, 2004). A meta-analysis suggests that even in samples without eating disorders, the Body Mass Index (BMI) typically increases during winter and is lowest in summer (Kuzmenko et al., 2021). Weight gain in the winter is plausibly explained by the tendencies to associate winter with high-calorie foods (Folwarczny et al., 2022) and to engage in fewer physical activities (Peiró-Velert et al., 2008). However, like for seasonal fluctuations of mood, it remains unknown whether people can predict their seasonal changes in appetite and associated weight gain outside of the winter season.

For seasonal fluctuations in sleep quality, findings are contradictory, and results might depend on the study site. A recent study in Germany did not find any significant differences in total sleep time when comparing winter and summer (Seidler et al., 2023). Similarly, a Japanese study found no effect of season on the prevalence of insomnia (Itani et al., 2016). Interestingly, a study in Finland found increased prevalence of insomnia symptoms and nightmares during winter among individuals with elevated symptoms of seasonal affective disorder (Sandman et al., 2016). It should be noted that seasonal changes in daylight availability are much more pronounced in the Northern parts of Finland as compared to Germany or Japan. However, also in a longitudinal Scandinavian study examining a healthy sample, the effect of season on sleep quality was small (Garde et al., 2014). Thus, it is possible that sleep problems are a seasonal problem for a specific portion of people in countries with long and dark winters. In line with this assumption, a recent survey among Icelandic women (Unnarsdóttir et al., 2022) found that almost one quarter of participants reported severe sleep problems which were more severe in winter. We postulate that more research is needed to find reliable predictors of low sleep quality in winter to effectively implement preventive measures for those who suffer from low sleep quality in specific seasons.

In summary, seasonal changes appear to affect some people more than others and it is possible that the affected domains differ between individuals. While some may experience low mood during the winter (Kasper et al., 1989), others may primarily struggle with poor sleep quality (Unnarsdóttir et al., 2022). To effectively assess the need for interventions and support services, it is essential to document the severity of symptom fluctuations across seasons. Additionally, to offer tailored interventions and preventive measures, it is important to understand how accurately individuals can assess and predict their own seasonal patterns, both in general and for specific symptoms. In the present study, we related self-reported seasonality in summer based on the SPAQ to longitudinal, seasonal (summer, autumn, winter, and spring) assessment of depression (as an indicator of mood seasonality), food cravings (indicating appetite seasonality), Body Mass Index (indicating body weight seasonality), insomnia (indicating sleep seasonality), and physical activity (indicating energy seasonality). This approach allowed for the investigation of the following research questions:

- 1) Is higher self-reported general seasonality (GSS of the SPAQ) predictive of more pronounced seasonal changes of (a) depression, (b) food cravings, (c) body weight, (d) insomnia, or (e) physical activity?
- 2) Is higher self-reported specific seasonality predictive for the respective domain-specific seasonal changes the domains of depression, food cravings, body weight as measured by the Body Mass Index (BMI), insomnia, and physical activity?

2. Materials & Methods

2.1. Participants

Icelandic residents aged between 19 and 75 years at the beginning of the one-year study in summer 2021 (age: $M = 43.2$ years, $SD = 12.9$ years; gender: $N_{female} = 266$, $N_{male} = 69$, $N_{other} = 1$) participated in the present study. Participants were recruited via advertisements on social media and word of mouth. Of these participants, 77 participants reported at least moderate seasonal changes (GSS above 10, see 2.2. Seasonality Assessments; age: $M = 38.3$ years, $SD = 11.8$ years; gender: $N_{female} = 65$, $N_{male} = 12$) and 102 reported no seasonal changes (GSS below 4; age: $M = 47.6$ years, $SD = 12.6$ years; gender: $N_{female} = 75$, $N_{male} = 26$, $N_{other} = 1$). Participants reporting at least moderate seasonal changes were on average younger than participants who reported no seasonal changes ($t(163) = 5.00$, $p < .001$, $d = 0.79$; compare Höller et al., 2021). Participants did not receive any financial compensation but the chance to win a gift card after completion of all four assessments. All participants provided written informed consent as part of the first page of the online form, and the study followed the Declaration of Helsinki. The National Bioethics Committee of Iceland approved the study [APPROVAL CODE WILL BE ADDED AFTER PEER REVIEW].

2.2. Seasonality Assessments

2.2.1. Self-reported Seasonality

The SPAQ (Magnusson, 1996) assesses the participants' self-reported seasonality of mood, appetite, weight, sleep, and energy (one item each ranging from 0 "no change" to 4 "extremely marked change") from which the GSS can be calculated. The GSS can range from 0 to 24 and is the sum of the five listed items and another sixth item assessing self-reported seasonality of socializing which was not assessed in the present study with a specific questionnaire. It has been suggested that a total GSS score above 10 indicates at least moderate seasonal changes (compare: Baek et al., 2015). In the present study, a GSS of 3 and lower (i.e., at least for half of the items no seasonal changes are reported) at the baseline assessment in summer was considered to be indicative of no (relevant) seasonal change. In line with the classification of GSS scores suggested by Kasper et al. (1989), SPAQ item scores above one on individual sub-scales (for mood, appetite, weight, sleep, and energy) indicated (at least) moderate seasonal changes. A score of zero indicated no seasonal changes. To ensure distinct seasonality groups that either clearly reported seasonal changes or no (relevant) seasonal changes, we focused on participants who reported at least moderate seasonal changes (GSS > 10; subscale scores > 1). Those who did not report any significant seasonal changes (GSS < 4; subscale score = 0) served as the comparison group. Consequently, we excluded data from participants with a GSS ranging from 4 to 10 or a subscale score of 1 (indicating a 'slight change') from the corresponding analyses (see results section for numbers of the overall sample and exclusions). In the present study, Cronbach's alpha for the GSS in summer was $\alpha = .83$.

2.2.2. Longitudinal Assessments of Seasonal Changes

For the SPAQ items mood, appetite, weight, sleep and energy, a corresponding measure was assessed once per season (i.e., repeated measures in summer, autumn, winter, and spring).

Mood was assessed using the Depression Anxiety Stress Scale (DASS) by Lovibond and Lovibond (1995). The DASS is a self-report scale that assesses indicators of depression, anxiety, and stress with either 42 or 21 items. In the present study, the 21-item short version was used. Each of the three subscales contains seven items for which respondents indicate how much a statement applied to them over the past week on a four-point Likert scale from 0: "Did not apply to me at all" to 3: "Applied to me very much, or most of the time". For the depression scale, Cronbach's alpha was $\alpha \geq .88$ in all seasons ($\alpha_{Summer} = .89$, $\alpha_{Autumn} = .92$, $\alpha_{Winter} = .88$, $\alpha_{Spring} = .90$).

Appetite was assessed via the intensity subscale of the Questionnaire on Cravings for Sweet or Rich Foods (QCSRF; Toll et al., 2008). The QCSRF intensity scale assesses the severity of cravings via

three items on a seven-point Likert scale from 1: “none at all” to 7: “more than ever”). Cronbach’s alpha was $\alpha \geq .92$ in each of the four assessments ($\alpha_{Summer} = .92$, $\alpha_{Autumn} = .92$, $\alpha_{Winter} = .94$, $\alpha_{Spring} = .94$).

Seasonal changes in body weight were assessed via the Body Mass Index (BMI).

Sleep quality was evaluated via the Bergen Insomnia Scale (BIS; Pallesen et al., 2008) which contains six items answered in number of days per week (i.e., 0 to 7). All four Cronbach’s alphas were $\alpha \geq .78$ ($\alpha_{Summer} = .78$, $\alpha_{Autumn} = .82$, $\alpha_{Winter} = .80$, $\alpha_{Spring} = .80$).

As an indicator of energy, activity was assessed longitudinally via the short form of the International Physical Activity Questionnaire (IPAQ-SF; Lee et al. 2011). In the IPAQ-SF the self-reported weekly duration of vigorous and moderate activity, as well as the time spent walking is used to calculate an estimate of the MET-minutes per week (MET: Metabolic Equivalent of Task).

2.3. Procedure

Participants were recruited via emails to distributors (e.g., large companies), social media, and among university students at the University of [WILL BE ADDED AFTER PEER REVIEW]. After participation in the baseline assessment between late spring and summer of 2021 (May to September), all respondents were contacted via email every 3 months to complete the same questionnaires once per season, for a total of four times.

2.4. Statistical Analyses

To investigate if self-reported seasonality can predict longitudinally assessed seasonal changes of mood, appetite, body weight, sleep, and energy, two by four linear mixed models (LMMs) with the factors seasonality (moderate changes, no changes as assessed in summer) and season (Summer, Autumn, Winter, Spring) were calculated (random intercepts across participants). For significant main effects of season, three post-hoc pairwise comparisons were calculated (Wilcoxon signed rank test) in which summer was compared to every other season. For significant interaction effects between seasonality and season, six Wilcoxon signed rank tests were calculated: Summer was compared to every other season once for the group who self-reported at least moderate seasonal changes in summer and once for the group that reported no seasonal changes in summer. Post-hoc pairwise comparisons were Bonferroni-adjusted for multiple comparison. Analyses were carried out using GAMLj (General Analyses for Linear Models in jamovi; version: 2.6.6) implemented in the statistical software jamovi (version 2.3).

3. Results

3.1. Sample statistics

Table 1 summarizes the group sizes and the distribution of self-reported seasonality (GSS and SPAQ items) from the baseline assessment in summer within these groups. For none of the groups, the sample size was smaller than $n = 65$. In Table 2, the group sizes for each season are summarized (again, the grouping is based on the SPAQ GSS at baseline in summer). After dropouts, the smallest group had a size of $n = 30$ (participants in spring who self-reported moderate changes of weight).

Table 1

Sample sizes and distribution of self-reported seasonality in summer.

Group	Moderate seasonality	No seasonality
GSS	<i>n</i> = 72, <i>median</i> = 13, <i>IQR</i> = 3	<i>n</i> = 98, <i>median</i> = 2, <i>IQR</i> = 2
SPAQ Mood	<i>n</i> = 146, <i>median</i> = 2, <i>IQR</i> = 1	<i>n</i> = 84, <i>median</i> = 0, <i>IQR</i> = 0
SPAQ Appetite	<i>n</i> = 78, <i>median</i> = 2, <i>IQR</i> = 1	<i>n</i> = 151, <i>median</i> = 0, <i>IQR</i> = 0
SPAQ Weight	<i>n</i> = 65, <i>median</i> = 2, <i>IQR</i> = 1	<i>n</i> = 150, <i>median</i> = 0, <i>IQR</i> = 0
SPAQ Sleep	<i>n</i> = 134, <i>median</i> = 2, <i>IQR</i> = 1	<i>n</i> = 72, <i>median</i> = 0, <i>IQR</i> = 0
SPAQ Energy	<i>n</i> = 111, <i>median</i> = 2, <i>IQR</i> = 1	<i>n</i> = 99, <i>median</i> = 0, <i>IQR</i> = 0

Note: *n* = sample size, *IQR* = interquartile ranges, grouped by the GSS (moderate change, no change), and SPAQ items for mood, appetite, weight, sleep and energy.

Table 2

Sample sizes in each season according to the grouping by the GSS score at baseline in summer.

Seasonality	Summer <i>N</i> = 336	Autumn <i>N</i> = 268	Winter <i>N</i> = 201	Spring <i>N</i> = 202
GSS				
No changes	<i>n</i> = 98	<i>n</i> = 76	<i>n</i> = 65	<i>n</i> = 64
Moderate changes	<i>n</i> = 72	<i>n</i> = 56	<i>n</i> = 40	<i>n</i> = 38
SPAQ Mood				
No changes	<i>n</i> = 84	<i>n</i> = 67	<i>n</i> = 53	<i>n</i> = 52
Moderate changes	<i>n</i> = 146	<i>n</i> = 117	<i>n</i> = 89	<i>n</i> = 85
SPAQ Appetite				
No changes	<i>n</i> = 151	<i>n</i> = 116	<i>n</i> = 89	<i>n</i> = 94
Moderate changes	<i>n</i> = 78	<i>n</i> = 67	<i>n</i> = 53	<i>n</i> = 47
SPAQ Weight				
No changes	<i>n</i> = 150	<i>n</i> = 122	<i>n</i> = 89	<i>n</i> = 96
Moderate changes	<i>n</i> = 65	<i>n</i> = 53	<i>n</i> = 37	<i>n</i> = 30
SPAQ Sleep				
No changes	<i>n</i> = 72	<i>n</i> = 55	<i>n</i> = 53	<i>n</i> = 52
Moderate changes	<i>n</i> = 134	<i>n</i> = 105	<i>n</i> = 77	<i>n</i> = 73
SPAQ Energy				
No changes	<i>n</i> = 99	<i>n</i> = 79	<i>n</i> = 67	<i>n</i> = 62
Moderate changes	<i>n</i> = 111	<i>n</i> = 91	<i>n</i> = 68	<i>n</i> = 65

Note: Grouped (moderate change, no change) by the GSS, and SPAQ items for mood, appetite, weight, sleep and energy. Please note that the overall *N* in the header counts also participants who were excluded because of their seasonality scores.

Figure 1 shows the distribution as box-plots for mood (DASS depression scale), appetite (QCSRF intensity scale), weight (BMI), sleep (BIS), and energy (IPAQ-SF) in each season and for each of the two seasonality groups. For the distributions within the excluded data (i.e., participants reported neither no seasonal changes nor at least moderate changes but slight seasonal changes on the SPAQ subscales or had a GSS from 4 to 10) see Supplementary Figure 1.

Figure 1. Box-plots for each season (summer, autumn, winter, spring) grouped by seasonality (red: moderate changes, blue: no change) of the GSS (left) or by the specific SPAQ item (right). 1st row: DASS Depression sum scores (possible range: 0 – 21; higher scores indicating higher depression); 2nd row: QCSRF Intensity mean scores (possible range: 1 – 7; higher scores indicating higher food craving intensity); 3rd row: BMI in kg/m²; 4th row: BIS sum scores (possible range: 0 – 42; higher scores indicating more frequent symptoms of insomnia); 5th row: IPAQ-SF estimations of MET-minutes per week.

3.2. Depression

3.2.1. Predicted by General Seasonality and Season (1a)

For depression according to the DASS depression scale, there was a significant main effect of seasonality (see Table 3): Participants who reported overall at least moderate seasonality also reported higher depression (DASS *mean* = 6.19, *SE* = 0.38) compared to participants reporting no seasonal changes (DASS *mean* = 1.58, *SE* = 0.32). Neither the main effect of the factor season, nor the interaction between season and seasonality were significant.

3.2.2. Predicted by Specific Mood Seasonality and Season (2a)

Similarly to the effect of general seasonality for depression, there was a significant main effect of seasonality of mood but neither a main effect of season nor an interaction of season and seasonality (Table 3). The seasonality effect was characterized by higher depression among participants reporting moderate seasonality of mood (DASS *mean* = 5.05, *SE* = 0.29) compared to participants reporting no seasonality of mood (DASS *mean* = 1.25, *SE* = 0.38).

3.3. Food Cravings

3.3.1. Predicted by General Seasonality and Season (1b)

For food craving intensity as indicated by the QCSRF, there was a significant main effect of seasonality (see Table 3): Self-reported moderate seasonality, were associated with lower craving intensity (QCSRF *mean* = 3.67, *SE* = 0.13) as compared to no seasonality (QCSRF *mean* = 4.71, *SE* = 0.11). Neither the main effect of season, nor the interaction between season and seasonality were significant.

3.3.2. Predicted by Specific Appetite Seasonality and Season (2b)

With the specific self-reported seasonality of appetite as a between-subject factor, both main effects but not their interaction were significant (see Table 3). The main effect of seasonality was characterized by lower craving intensity of participants with moderate self-reported seasonality (QCSRF *mean* = 3.74, *SE* = 0.12) compared to no self-reported seasonality (QCSRF *mean* = 4.53, *SE* = 0.09). The main effect of season was caused by lower craving intensity in summer (QCSRF *mean* = 4.00, *SE* = 0.09) than in winter (QCSRF *mean* = 4.24, *SE* = 0.10; $W = 2662$, $p_{\text{bonferroni}} = .048$, $r_{\text{rb}} = .254$) and in spring (QCSRF *mean* = 4.27, *SE* = 0.11; $W = 2602$, $p_{\text{bonferroni}} = .021$, $r_{\text{rb}} = .283$). However, there was no significant difference between summer and autumn (QCSRF *mean* = 4.03, *SE* = 0.10; $W = 4897$, $p_{\text{bonferroni}} = .714$).

3.4. BMI

3.4.1. Predicted by General Seasonality and Season (1c)

For the BMI, the main effect of seasonality was significant, and the effect was characterized by a higher BMI of participants with moderate self-reported seasonality (BMI *mean* = 29.4 kg/m², *SE* = 0.7 kg/m²) compared to no self-reported seasonality (BMI *mean* = 27.0 kg/m², *SE* = 0.6 kg/m²). There was no effect of season, and no interaction between seasonality and season (Table 3).

3.4.2. Predicted by Specific Weight Seasonality and Season (2c)

With specific self-reported weight seasonality as a predictor, the main effect of seasonality but neither the effect of season nor the interaction was significant (Table 3). The effect of seasonality was characterized by a higher BMI of participants with higher seasonality (BMI *mean* = 29.7 kg/m², *SE* = 0.7 kg/m²) compared to participants with no self-reported changes in weight (BMI *mean* = 26.8 kg/m², *SE* = 0.4 kg/m²).

3.5. Insomnia

3.5.1. Predicted by General Seasonality and Season (1d)

For insomnia (BIS), there was a significant main effect of seasonality (Table 3): Moderate seasonality was associated with higher insomnia (BIS *mean* = 18.8, *SE* = 0.9) than no seasonality (BIS *mean* = 11.0, *SE* = 0.8). Neither the main effect of season nor the interaction between seasonality and season were significant.

3.5.2. Predicted by Specific Sleep Seasonality and Season (2d)

Also, with specific seasonality of sleep as a predictor, there was only a main effect of seasonality, but neither was there a main effect of season nor a significant interaction effect (Table 3). Insomnia of participants reporting moderate seasonality (BIS *mean* = 15.8, *SE* = 0.8) was higher than insomnia of participants reporting no seasonality of sleep (BIS *mean* = 12.6, *SE* = 1.0).

3.6. Physical Activity

3.6.1. Predicted by General Seasonality and Season (1e)

Physical Activity (IPAQ-SF) was affected by season and general seasonality. However, there was no interaction between season and seasonality (Table 3). Overall participants with a higher self-reported seasonality had fewer MET minutes per week (IPAQ-SF *mean* = 1319 MET-min/week, *SE* = 204 MET-min/week) than participants who reported no seasonality (IPAQ-SF *mean* = 2024 MET-min/week, *SE* = 169 MET-min/week). The effect of season was characterized by a higher number of MET minutes per week in summer (IPAQ-SF *mean* = 2403 MET-min/week, *SE* = 157 MET-min/week) compared to autumn (IPAQ-SF *mean* = 1695 MET-min/week, *SE* = 172 MET-min/week; $W = 2958$, $p_{\text{bonferroni}} = .009$, $r_{\text{rb}} = .353$), to winter (IPAQ-SF *mean* = 1599 MET-min/week, *SE* = 190 MET-min/week; $W = 1935$, $p_{\text{bonferroni}} < .001$, $r_{\text{rb}} = .557$), and to spring (IPAQ-SF *mean* = 990 MET-min/week, *SE* = 206 MET-min/week; $W = 1726$, $p_{\text{bonferroni}} < .001$, $r_{\text{rb}} = .768$).

3.6.2. Predicted by Specific Energy Seasonality and Season (2e)

When seasonality was defined by specific seasonal changes of energy, also, both main effects on physical activity were significant but not the interaction between seasonality and season (Table 3). Overall, participants with a higher self-reported seasonality had fewer MET minutes per week (IPAQ-SF *mean* = 1644 MET-min/week, *SE* = 164 MET-min/week) than participants who reported no seasonality (IPAQ-SF *mean* = 2200 MET-min/week, *SE* = 172 MET-min/week). The effect of season was characterized by a higher number of MET minutes per week in summer (IPAQ-SF *mean* = 2623 MET-min/week, *SE* = 145 MET-min/week) compared to autumn (IPAQ-SF *mean* = 1934 MET-min/week, *SE* = 157 MET-min/week; $W = 4084$, $p_{\text{bonferroni}} = .006$, $r_{\text{rb}} = .338$), to winter (IPAQ-SF *mean* = 1857 MET-min/week, *SE* = 171 MET-min/week; $W = 2649$, $p_{\text{bonferroni}} < .001$, $r_{\text{rb}} = .416$), and to spring (IPAQ-SF *mean* = 1275 MET-min/week, *SE* = 180 MET-min/week; $W = 2850$, $p_{\text{bonferroni}} < .001$, $r_{\text{rb}} = .759$).

Table 3

Main effects of Seasonality (no changes, at least moderate changes), Season (Summer, Autumn, Winter, Spring) and their interaction.

Fixed Effect Omnibus Test		
DV: DASS Depr.	Seasonality grouping by GSS	Seasonality grouping by SPAQ Mood
Seasonality	$F(1, 171) = 84.98, p < .001^{***}$	$F(1, 231) = 64.09, p < .001^{***}$
Season	$F(3, 346) = 0.54, p = .658$	$F(3, 472) = 0.84, p = .471$
Interaction	$F(3, 346) = 0.73, p = .535$	$F(3, 472) = 0.77, p = .512$
DV: QCSRF Int.	Seasonality grouping by GSS	Seasonality grouping by SPAQ App.
Seasonality	$F(1, 176) = 36.39, p < .001^{***}$	$F(1, 231) = 25.84, p < .001^{***}$
Season	$F(3, 354) = 1.03, p = .378$	$F(3, 482) = 3.66, p = .012^*$
Interaction	$F(3, 354) = 1.73, p = .160$	$F(3, 482) = 1.58, p = .193$
DV: BMI	Seasonality grouping by GSS	Seasonality grouping by SPAQ Weight
Seasonality	$F(1, 168) = 6.72, p = .010^*$	$F(1, 213) = 13.44, p < .001^{***}$
Season	$F(3, 332) = 1.48, p = .220$	$F(3, 421) = 2.53, p = .057$
Interaction	$F(3, 332) = 0.89, p = .445$	$F(3, 421) = 0.83, p = .478$
DV: BIS	Seasonality grouping by GSS	Seasonality grouping by SPAQ Sleep
Seasonality	$F(1, 171) = 40.58, p < .001^{***}$	$F(1, 203) = 6.45, p = .012^*$
Season	$F(3, 346) = 0.28, p = .837$	$F(3, 420) = 0.40, p = .750$
Interaction	$F(3, 346) = 0.28, p = .578$	$F(3, 420) = 0.24, p = .867$
DV: IPAQ-SF	Seasonality grouping by GSS	Seasonality grouping by SPAQ Energy
Seasonality	$F(1, 164) = 7.09, p = .009^{**}$	$F(1, 193) = 5.49, p = .020^*$
Season	$F(3, 272) = 17.09, p < .001^{***}$	$F(3, 343) = 18.60, p < .001^{***}$
Interaction	$F(3, 272) = 0.92, p = .432$	$F(3, 343) = 2.31, p = .076$

Note: DV = dependent variable. DASS Depr. = DASS Depression scale. QCSRF Int. = QCSRF Intensity scale. SPAQ App. = SPAQ Appetite scale. $*p < .05$, $**p < .01$, $***p < .001$

4. Discussion

In the present study we examined whether the SPAQ GSS overall or specific subscales of the SPAQ GSS for seasonality of mood, sleep, weight, appetite, and physical activity would predict seasonal changes in the respective domains. To confirm that the SPAQ GSS as well as the SPAQ subscales can reliably predict seasonal changes in these domains we would have expected an interaction between the SPAQ, grouping individuals into those with at least moderate and those with low seasonal changes, and season, i.e., higher actual seasonal fluctuations in those with self-reported higher seasonality. However, for none of the domains, there was the expected significant interaction between reported seasonality and season.

4.1. Seasonality

All the assessed domains were significantly associated with seasonality, with more depression, higher weight, more insomnia symptoms, and less physical activity among individuals who rated themselves to experience at least moderate seasonality overall, as well as in the specific domain of mood, weight, sleep, and energy. Furthermore, food craving was significantly associated with seasonality, but paradoxically we found that individuals who reported more seasonal symptoms (overall and specifically appetite) reported less food cravings.

According to our data, overall higher depressive symptoms were linked to both general seasonality as well as the mood-specific subdomain of the SPAQ. Participants who reported more pronounced seasonal fluctuations of their mood also reported higher depressive symptoms in all seasons.

Like for non-seasonal depression (Tsuno et al., 2005), it was shown in the past that self-reported seasonality is associated with sleep problems (Øyane et al., 2008; Höller et al., 2021; Luo et al., 2024), which is well in line with our data. A higher self-reported seasonality was associated with higher symptoms of insomnia but not with seasonal fluctuations of these symptoms. In a previous study, worsening of mood in the winter could be predicted by self-reported sleep problems in summer (Höller et al. 2022). In the present study, we observed no seasonal fluctuations of mood and, thus, this association could not be further investigated.

The relation between body weight and seasonality has been documented extensively and is assumed to be caused by changes in appetite and carbohydrate intake (Wurtman, 1993; Kräuchi et al., 1997). However, there is also research suggesting that changes in diet do not necessarily come with changes in BMI (Kräuchi and Wirz-Justice, 1988). In our data we found that both food cravings and BMI differed between people with moderate and low self-reported seasonality of appetite or weight. However, seasonal fluctuations were not observed in either of the groups.

Physical activity is among the recommended lifestyle changes to remediate the negative impact of seasonal affective disorder, although it must be noted that clear clinical evidence for the effectiveness of this intervention is lacking (Rothenberg et al., 2024). Like in our sample, reduced physical activity was reported to be related to increased seasonal sensitivity (Alvarado et al., 2023). We speculate that those who are at lower risk for seasonal symptoms are more likely to engage in physical activity throughout the year. The most difficult result to explain is the lower food craving for people with higher seasonality. While the overall consensus is that individuals with seasonal affective disorder exhibit more cravings for starch-rich food (Yang et al., 2020) it was found that they do not like sweetness more than controls (Swiecicki et al., 2015). It is possible that prior reports for food cravings depend on the local culture of the place where the study was conducted. For example, it was suggested that fatty food cravings might be normal in the winter in locations at a high Northern latitude (Lingjaerde and Reichborn-Kjennerud, 1993). It is, thus, possible that our finding of less food cravings in the higher-seasonality group is due to the local culture. It is also worth noting that seasonal affective disorder exists in (at least) two variants, namely winter and summer depression, with potentially different patterns of symptoms. Winter depression is said to be characterized by weight gain, craving for carbohydrates, increased appetite, and hypersomnia, but summer depression comes with decreased appetite and insomnia (Wehr et al., 1991). However, other research suggests that symptoms might be similar across the two variants of seasonal affective disorder (Rosen and Rosenthal, 1991). With respect to our paradoxical finding of less cravings in the higher seasonality group it is possible that the symptom profile of seasonal affective disorder interacts with the local culture. Another possible explanation is that in our Icelandic sample overall the seasonal decrease in appetite during summer was relatively stronger as compared to a seasonal increase in appetite in winter.

4.2. Seasonal Changes

In contrast to the common usage of the SPAQ GSS to indicate seasonal depression, there was no association between the overall or domain specific score of the SPAQ and seasonal changes in mood according to the DASS. However, we did not detect any seasonal fluctuation of mood at all in the present sample, which limits conclusions in this respect. Since seasonal mood did not fluctuate, it was difficult to predict those fluctuations. Surprisingly, variation in the data was too low even though we

selected participants according to their subjective indication of experiencing at least moderate changes over the seasons. Similarly, there was neither a seasonal change in insomnia symptoms, nor a seasonal pattern in weight. Hence, there was no interaction between seasonality and insomnia symptoms or weight.

Notably, only appetite and physical activity showed significant fluctuations with the seasons, but in no domain this seasonal fluctuation significantly interacted with specific or general self-reported seasonality. Hence, self-reported seasonality did not predict longitudinally assessed fluctuations.

The SPAQ is widely disputed as a tool for detecting seasonal affective disorder, because of memory and confirmation bias (Nayar and Cochrane, 1996), low reliability and validity (Mersch et al., 2004) and the poor representation of actual depression in the constructed items (Traffanstedt et al., 2016). According to our data, we must consider the possibility that for those domains where we detected seasonal changes but no interaction between seasonality and seasonal changes that the SPAQ is not well suited to predict actual seasonal symptoms. This is true for the domains of appetite and physical activity, while for the other domains of mood, sleep, and weight we simply did not detect any seasonal changes and no conclusion is possible. Nevertheless, the overall lack of seasonal changes on most SPAQ subscales but still elevated seasonality scores on some subscales is well in line with the previously raised criticism that the SPAQ might overestimate seasonality (Øverland et al., 2019).

One possible interpretation of our data is that individuals who are more likely to report high seasonality are also more likely to report other symptoms, or mental health symptoms in general, and that these reports might overestimate the actual problem and, hence, lead to poor validity of measurements of seasonality based on the SPAQ.

4.3. Limitations

Like in every longitudinal study, our sample decreased over the course of the follow ups, limiting the conclusions in two ways. Firstly, the smaller sample size decreased statistical power, and secondly, it is possible that dropouts happened systematically. Specifically, we cannot rule out the possibility that participants who actually experienced depression at any follow-up would have skipped participation because of their depression symptoms. In other words, decreased mental health can lead to lower availability to answer a questionnaire about mental health, because any additional task could seem overwhelming. Consequentially, we cannot rule out that the limited variability of depression even in participants who reported a high seasonality of mood, may have been due to states of particularly high depression not being included in the data.

Another bias in the sample lies in the fact that the present study resulted from convenience sampling. The study was advertised among students and social media as the “SAD food study” (SAD standing for seasonal affective disorder), and it is likely that people with interest in seasonal affective disorder and nutrition answered the questionnaire.

Notably, the group with elevated general seasonality was younger in our sample than the group with no seasonal pattern. The risk profile (Höller et al., 2021) and symptom pattern of seasonal affective disorder is moderated by age (Lukmanji et al., 2020). While adults report mainly fluctuations of sleep and appetite, adolescents and young adults (12-24 years) report a broad symptom pattern affecting interest, mood, sleep, energy, appetite, and cognitive symptoms (Lukmanji et al., 2020). Although we found a rather narrow range of seasonal changes, age difference between groups might have affected our results.

Furthermore, since we did not detect significant seasonal fluctuations in all domains other than food craving and activity, we cannot conclude that the SPAQ is not a valid instrument to predict

seasonal changes, since our sample might just have demonstrated too little variability in these domains. If future studies observe more pronounced seasonal fluctuations of domains covered by the SPAQ, it should be investigated whether more pronounced seasonal fluctuations are associated with higher self-reported seasonality as assessed in the SPAQ.

Unfortunately, the study did not include a questionnaire on socializing in the original concept of the study, such that this sub-scale of the SPAQ could not be assessed with respect to its predictive validity. Future studies should include this factor, even though socializing is not a core concept of seasonal depression assessed in comparable questionnaires that screen for seasonal affective disorder such as the Seasonal Health Questionnaire (Thompson & Cowan, 2001).

Finally, our results may be limited to the SPAQ, as there exist other instruments to screen for seasonal affective disorder such as the Seasonal Health Questionnaire (Thompson & Cowan, 2001).

5 Conclusions

While the SPAQ is commonly used to screen for seasonal affective disorder, our study indicates that it failed to predict seasonal changes. The study is limited insofar as we did not detect significant seasonal changes in mood and insomnia symptoms, as well as body weight. Thus, we cannot draw conclusions on the validity of the instrument in these regards. However, overall, our results emphasize the challenge of obtaining a valid parameter to predict seasonal depression based on a single assessment. To actually diagnose seasonal affective disorder it might be recommendable to perform a longitudinal follow-up on affected individuals in order to confirm the seasonal pattern.

6. References

- Alvarado, C., Castillo-Aguilar, M., Villegas, V., Estrada Goic, C., Harris, K., Barria, P., Moraes, M. M., Mendes, T. T., Arantes, R. M. E., Valdés-Badilla, P., & Núñez-Espinosa, C. (2023). Physical Activity, Seasonal Sensitivity and Psychological Well-Being of People of Different Age Groups Living in Extreme Environments. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 20(3). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20031719>
- American Psychiatric Association. (2013). *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders*. American Psychiatric Association. <https://doi.org/10.1176/appi.books.9780890425596>
- Baek, J. H., Kim, J. S., Huh, I., Lee, K., Park, J. H., Park, T., Ha, K., & Hong, K. S. (2015). Prevalence, behavioral manifestations and associated individual and climatic factors of seasonality in the Korean general population. *Comprehensive Psychiatry*, 57, 148–154. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.comppsy.2014.10.014>
- Folwarczny, M., Otterbring, T., Sigurdsson, V., & Gasiorowska, A. (2022). Seasonal cues to food scarcity and calorie cravings: Winter cues elicit preferences for energy-dense foods. *Food Quality and Preference*, 96, 104379. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodqual.2021.104379>
- Garde, A. H., Hansen, Å. M., Persson, R., Österberg, K., Ørbæk, P., Karlson, B., Olsen, A., & Kristiansen, J. (2014). Month-to-month variation in sleep among healthy, Scandinavian daytime workers. *Scandinavian Journal of Clinical and Laboratory Investigation*, 74(6), 527–535. <https://doi.org/10.3109/00365513.2014.913303>
- Höller, Y., Gudjónsdóttir, B. E., Valgeirsdóttir, S. K., & Heimisson, G. T. (2021). The effect of age and chronotype on seasonality, sleep problems, and mood. *Psychiatry Research*, 297, 113722. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2021.113722>
- Höller, Y., Urbschat, M. M., Kristófersson, G. K., & Ólafsson, R. P. (2022). Predictability of Seasonal Mood Fluctuations Based on Self-Report Questionnaires and EEG Biomarkers in a Non-clinical Sample. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 13, 870079. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2022.870079>

- Itani, O., Kaneita, Y., Munezawa, T., Mishima, K., Jike, M., Nakagome, S., Tokiya, M., & Ohida, T. (2016). Nationwide epidemiological study of insomnia in Japan. *Sleep Medicine*, 25, 130–138. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sleep.2016.05.013>
- Kasper, S [S.], Wehr, T. A., Bartko, J. J., Gaist, P. A., & Rosenthal, N. E. (1989). Epidemiological findings of seasonal changes in mood and behavior. A telephone survey of Montgomery County, Maryland. *Archives of General Psychiatry*, 46(9), 823–833. <https://doi.org/10.1001/archpsyc.1989.01810090065010>
- Kräuchi, K., Reich, S., & Wirz-Justice, A. (1997). Eating style in seasonal affective disorder: Who will gain weight in winter? *Comprehensive Psychiatry*, 38(2), 80–87. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0010-440x\(97\)90085-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0010-440x(97)90085-7)
- Kräuchi, K., & Wirz-Justice, A. (1988). The four seasons: Food intake frequency in seasonal affective disorder in the course of a year. *Psychiatry Research*, 25(3), 323–338. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-1781\(88\)90102-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-1781(88)90102-3)
- Kuzmenko, N. V., Tsyrlin, V. A., Pliss, M. G., & Galagudza, M. M. (2021). Seasonal Body Weight Dynamics in Healthy People: A Meta-Analysis. *Human Physiology*, 47(6), 676–689. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S0362119721060062>
- Lee, P. H., Macfarlane, D. J., Lam, T. H., & Stewart, S. M. (2011). Validity of the International Physical Activity Questionnaire Short Form (IPAQ-SF): A systematic review. *The International Journal of Behavioral Nutrition and Physical Activity*, 8, 115. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1479-5868-8-115>
- Lingjaerde, O., & Reichborn-Kjennerud, T. (1993). Characteristics of winter depression in the Oslo area (60 degrees N). *Acta Psychiatrica Scandinavica*, 88(2), 111–120. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0447.1993.tb03423.x>
- Lovibond, P. F., & Lovibond, S. H. (1995). The structure of negative emotional states: Comparison of the Depression Anxiety Stress Scales (DASS) with the Beck Depression and Anxiety Inventories. *Behaviour Research and Therapy*, 33(3), 335–343. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0005-7967\(94\)00075-U](https://doi.org/10.1016/0005-7967(94)00075-U)
- Lukmanji, A., Williams, J. V. A., Bulloch, A. G. M., & Patten, S. B. (2020). Seasonal variation in specific depressive symptoms: A population based study. *Journal of Affective Disorders*, 261, 153–159. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2019.10.003>
- Luo, H., Cheng, J [Juan], Zhang, Z., Zhang, Y., Wang, X., Hu, R., Li, J., Guo, Y., & Luo, Q. (2024). Seasonal patterns in Chinese population: Validating the seasonal pattern assessment questionnaire and exploring associations with psychiatric diagnoses and biological rhythms. *Chronobiology International*, 41(5), 609–620. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07420528.2024.2337875>
- Ma, Y., Olendzki, B. C., Li, W., Hafner, A. R., Chiriboga, D., Hebert, J. R., Campbell, M., Sarnie, M., & Ockene, I. S. (2006). Seasonal variation in food intake, physical activity, and body weight in a predominantly overweight population. *European Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, 60(4), 519–528. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sj.ejcn.1602346>
- Magnusson, A. (1996). Validation of the Seasonal Pattern Assessment Questionnaire (SPAQ). *Journal of Affective Disorders*, 40(3), 121–129. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-0327\(96\)00036-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-0327(96)00036-5)
- Magnusson, A., Axelsson, J., Karlsson, M. M., & Oskarsson, H. (2000). Lack of seasonal mood change in the Icelandic population: Results of a cross-sectional study. *The American Journal of Psychiatry*, 157(2), 234–238. <https://doi.org/10.1176/appi.ajp.157.2.234>
- Mersch, P. P. A., Vastenburger, N. C., Meesters, Y., Bouhuys, A. L., Beersma, D. G. M., van den Hoofdakker, R. H., & Boer, J. A. den (2004). The reliability and validity of the Seasonal Pattern Assessment Questionnaire: A comparison between patient groups. *Journal of Affective Disorders*, 80(2-3), 209–219. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0165-0327\(03\)00114-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0165-0327(03)00114-9)
- Nayyar, K., & Cochrane, R. (1996). Seasonal changes in affective state measured prospectively and retrospectively. *The British Journal of Psychiatry : The Journal of Mental Science*, 168(5), 627–632. <https://doi.org/10.1192/bjp.168.5.627>

- Øverland, S., Woicik, W., Sikora, L., Whittaker, K., Heli, H., Skjelkvåle, F. S., Sivertsen, B., & Colman, I. (2019). Seasonality and symptoms of depression: A systematic review of the literature. *Epidemiology and Psychiatric Sciences*, 29, e31. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S2045796019000209>
- Øyane, N. M., Ursin, R., Pallesen, S., Holsten, F., & Bjørvatn, B. (2008). Self-reported seasonality is associated with complaints of sleep problems and deficient sleep duration: The Hordaland Health Study. *Journal of Sleep Research*, 17(1), 63–72. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2869.2008.00628.x>
- Pallesen, S., Bjorvatn, B., Nordhus, I. H., Sivertsen, B., Hjørnevik, M., & Morin, C. M. (2008). A new scale for measuring insomnia: the Bergen Insomnia Scale. *Percept Mot Skills*, 107(3), 691-706. <https://doi.org/10.2466/pms.107.3.691-706>
- Peiró-Velert, C., Devís-Devís, J., Beltrán-Carrillo, V. J., & Fox, K. R. (2008). Variability of Spanish adolescents' physical activity patterns by seasonality, day of the week and demographic factors. *European Journal of Sport Science*, 8(3), 163–171. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17461390802020868>
- Pjrek, E [E.], Baldinger-Melich, P., Spies, M., Papageorgiou, K., Kasper, S [S.], & Winkler, D [D.] (2016). Epidemiology and socioeconomic impact of seasonal affective disorder in Austria. *European Psychiatry : The Journal of the Association of European Psychiatrists*, 32, 28–33. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eurpsy.2015.11.001>
- Rosen, L. N., & Rosenthal, N. E. (1991). Seasonal variations in mood and behavior in the general population: A factor-analytic approach. *Psychiatry Research*, 38(3), 271–283. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-1781\(91\)90017-j](https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-1781(91)90017-j)
- Rothenberg, M., Nussbaumer-Streit, B., Pjrek, E [Edda], & Winkler, D [Dietmar] (2024). Lifestyle modification as intervention for seasonal affective disorder: A systematic review. *Journal of Psychiatric Research*, 174, 209–219. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpsychires.2024.03.053>
- Sandman, N., Merikanto, I., Määttänen, H., Valli, K., Kronholm, E., Laatikainen, T., Partonen, T., & Paunio, T. (2016). Winter is coming: Nightmares and sleep problems during seasonal affective disorder. *Journal of Sleep Research*, 25(5), 612–619. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jsr.12416>
- Seidler, A., Wehrich, K. S., Bes, F., Zeeuw, J. de, & Kunz, D. (2023). Seasonality of human sleep: Polysomnographic data of a neuropsychiatric sleep clinic. *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, 17, 1105233. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnins.2023.1105233>
- Spence, C. (2021). Explaining seasonal patterns of food consumption. *International Journal of Gastronomy and Food Science*, 24, 100332. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijgfs.2021.100332>
- Swiecicki, L., Scinska, A., Bzinkowska, D., Torbinski, J., Sienkiewicz-Jarosz, H., Samochowiec, J., & Bienkowski, P. (2015). Intensity and pleasantness of sucrose taste in patients with winter depression. *Nutritional Neuroscience*, 18(4), 186–191. <https://doi.org/10.1179/1476830514y.0000000115>
- Thompson, C., & Cowan, A. (2001). The Seasonal Health Questionnaire: a preliminary validation of a new instrument to screen for seasonal affective disorder. *Journal of Affective Disorders*, 64(1), 89-98. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0165-0327\(00\)00208-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0165-0327(00)00208-1)
- Thompson, C., Thompson, S., & Smith, R. (2004). Prevalence of seasonal affective disorder in primary care; a comparison of the seasonal health questionnaire and the seasonal pattern assessment questionnaire. *Journal of Affective Disorders*, 78(3), 219–226. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0165-0327\(02\)00314-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0165-0327(02)00314-2)
- Toll, B. A., Katulak, N. A., Williams-Piehot, P., & O'Malley, S. (2008). Validation of a scale for the assessment of food cravings among smokers. *Appetite*, 50(1), 25–32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.appet.2007.05.001>
- Traffanstedt, M. K., Mehta, S., & LoBello, S. G. (2016). Major Depression With Seasonal Variation. *Clinical Psychological Science*, 4(5), 825–834. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2167702615615867>

- Tsuno, N., Besset, A., & Ritchie, K. (2005). Sleep and depression. *The Journal of Clinical Psychiatry*, *66*(10), 1254–1269. <https://doi.org/10.4088/jcp.v66n1008>
- Unnarsdóttir, A. B., Hauksdóttir, A., Aspelund, T., Gunnarsdóttir, V., Tómasson, G., Jakobsdóttir, J., Valdimarsdóttir, U. A., & Thordardottir, E. B. (2022). Sleep disturbances among women in a Subarctic region: A nationwide study. *Sleep*, *45*(8). <https://doi.org/10.1093/sleep/zsac100>
- Visscher, T. L. S., & Seidell, J. C. (2004). Time trends (1993-1997) and seasonal variation in body mass index and waist circumference in the Netherlands. *International Journal of Obesity and Related Metabolic Disorders : Journal of the International Association for the Study of Obesity*, *28*(10), 1309–1316. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sj.ijo.0802761>
- Wehr, T. A., Giesen, H. A., Schulz, P. M., Anderson, J. L., Joseph-Vanderpool, J. R., Kelly, K., Kasper, S [S.], & Rosenthal, N. E. (1991). Contrasts between symptoms of summer depression and winter depression. *Journal of Affective Disorders*, *23*(4), 173–183. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-0327\(91\)90098-d](https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-0327(91)90098-d)
- Winkler, D [Dietmar], Reichardt, B., Kranz, G. S., Bartova, L., Kasper, S [Siegfried], & Pjrek, E [Edda] (2019). Seasonality of antidepressant prescriptions and sick leaves. *Journal of Psychiatric Research*, *111*, 128–133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpsychires.2019.01.020>
- Winthorst, W. H., Bos, E. H., Roest, A. M., & Jonge, P. de (2020). Seasonality of mood and affect in a large general population sample. *PloS One*, *15*(9), e0239033. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0239033>
- Wurtman, J. J. (1993). Depression and weight gain: The serotonin connection. *Journal of Affective Disorders*, *29*(2-3), 183–192. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-0327\(93\)90032-f](https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-0327(93)90032-f)
- Yang, Y., Zhang, S., Zhang, X., Xu, Y., Cheng, J [Junrui], & Yang, X. (2020). The Role of Diet, Eating Behavior, and Nutrition Intervention in Seasonal Affective Disorder: A Systematic Review. *Frontiers in Psychology*, *11*, 1451. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.01451>